

**DEVELOPMENT OF FACIAL RECOGNITION SYSTEM FOR DETECTING AND
RECOGNIZING FACES**

BY

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CERTIFICATION

This is to certify that the project upon which this report is based was carried out by **EMAH, ARCHIBONG EMMANUEL** with matriculation number: **EEE/15/2407** in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the award of B.Eng. degree in the department of Electrical and Electronics Engineering, Federal University of Technology, Akure. Ondo State.

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DEDICATION

I will gladly offer you a sacrifice, O LORD; I will give you thanks because you are good. You have rescued me from all my troubles, and I have seen my enemies defeated (Psalms 54:6-7).

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This project would not have been possible without the unfailing mercies of GOD ALMIGHTY; I sincerely appreciate my maker for His protection and inspiration throughout my stay in this citadel of learning.

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ABSTRACT

This project demonstrates how we can use image processing to implement face detection and recognition algorithms to develop a system that can detect and recognize individual faces. Oxford Dictionary defines a face as the front part of a person's head from the forehead to the chin, or the corresponding part of an animal. In human interactions, the face is the most important factor as it contains important information about a person or individual. The problem humans encounter is that they cannot identify all the individuals in a particular area due to the large number of people in that area and due to the fact that the human brain cannot keep records of all the individuals in that area, it will be difficult for any human to identify and recognize a particular individual. The proposed solution for this problem is to develop a working system that will detect the frontal faces of individuals. The second part of the system will also be able to perform a facial recognition against a small database. The development of the system will help to easily identify any individual. In recent years, research has been carried out and face recognition and detection systems have been developed. Some of which are used on social media platforms, banking apps, government offices e.g. the Metropolitan Police, Facebook etc.

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CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of Study

The face is regarded as the most important part of the human body. According to research, even a face can speak, and it has different words for different emotions. It is essential in interacting with people in society. It conveys people's identities and can thus be used as a key in many organizations' security solutions. The facial recognition system is becoming increasingly popular around the world as an extremely safe and dependable security technology. Because of its high level of security and dependability, it is gaining significant importance and attention from thousands of corporate and government organizations.

Furthermore, when compared to other biometric security solutions such as palmprints and fingerprints, the facial recognition system offers significant advantages. The system measures a person's biometrics from a specific distance without interacting with the person. This system can assist many organizations in identifying a person who has a criminal record or other legal issues in crime deterrent applications. As a result, this technology is becoming increasingly important for a wide range of residential buildings and corporate organizations. This technique is based on the ability to recognize a human face and then compare its various features to previously recorded faces. This feature also increases the system's importance and allows it to be widely used around the world. It is designed with user-friendly features and operations that include various facial nodal points. A face has approximately 80 to 90 distinct nodal points. The facial recognition system measures important aspects such as the distance between the eyes, the length of the jawline, the shape of the cheekbones, and the depth of the eyes using these nodal points. These points are

calculated by generating a code known as the faceprint, which represents the identity of the face in a computer database.

Faces are frequently used by humans to identify individuals. Similar recognition is now possible automatically thanks to advancements in computing capabilities over the years. Face recognition is a pattern recognition task that is typically applied to human faces. Humans are exceptionally adept at recognizing faces and complex patterns. Even the passage of time has no effect on these capabilities, so it would be beneficial if computers could become as robust as humans in face recognition. Face recognition systems can be useful in a variety of ways; they can be used for both verification and identification. Today, recognition technology is used to solve a wide range of problems, including passport fraud and human-computer interaction.

1.2 Face Detection

Face detection is the process of locating a face in a given image and separating it from the rest of the scene. Visual pattern detection is a significant and difficult problem. The first step in most automatic vision systems is the automatic detection of targets. The majority of computer vision research is based on the robust detection and accurate location of objects within the tested images. Algorithms for automatic, visual detection of targets are not always provided. In other cases, rather ineffective algorithms are used, which are based on assumptions (such as a controlled environment) that are inappropriate for real-world applications. Despite the fact that it appears to be a simple task for a human vision system, machine detection of visual patterns is difficult due to the wide range of variations present in real-time data. Aside from the intra-class variation inherent in any family of objects, this pattern detection method must contend with other sources of image variation such as light conditions, object pose, imaging system, and so on. When viewed as a pattern, the face is a difficult object to detect and recognize. The face anatomy is rigid enough that

all faces have a similar structure, but we are very different. In addition to individual and racial variations, there are facial expressions, which allow an individual to significantly alter his or her appearance. The main approaches for pattern recognition have been used in the detection of faces and facial features. However, a comprehensive evaluation and comparison of these techniques is difficult due to the large number of factors to consider, such as the training set, the testing set, computational requirements, and other testing conditions

1.3 Face Recognition

Face recognition is done at the subordinate level. At this point, a new face is compared to face models stored in a database, and if a match is found, the new face is assigned to a known individual. Face identification performance is influenced by several factors, including scale, pose, illumination, facial expression, and disguise. A rescaling process can handle the scale of a face. Multiple trials can be used to determine the scaling factor in the Eigen-face approach. The idea is to use multistate Eigen-faces, which compare a test face image to Eigen-faces at various scales. In this case, the image will appear to be close to face space, with only the closest scaled Eigen-faces visible. We can also scale the test image to different sizes and use the scaling factor that results in the shortest distance to face space. Changes in viewpoint or head orientation cause varying poses. Different identification algorithms exhibit varying sensitivity to pose variation. Identifying faces in varying luminance conditions is a difficult problem for face recognition. The same person, with the same facial expression and viewed from the same angle, can appear drastically different as the lighting changes. To handle different lighting conditions, two approaches, the fisher-face space approach and the illumination subspace approach, have been proposed in recent years. In order to maximize between-class scatter while minimizing within-class scatter, the fisher-face method projects face images onto a three-dimensional linear subspace based on Fisher's Linear

Discriminant. The illumination subspace method creates an illumination cone of a face from a series of images taken in unknown lighting conditions. This latter approach is said to perform significantly better, especially under extreme lighting conditions. In contrast to the effects of scale, pose, and illumination, facial expression can significantly alter the geometry of a face. Attempts in computer graphics have been made to model facial expressions from a muscular standpoint. Another issue that face recognition encounters in practice is disguise. Glasses, hairstyles, and makeup all alter the appearance of a person's face. So far, most research has focused solely on the issue of glasses.

1.4 Aim and Objective of Study

1.4.1 Aim

This study aims to develop facial recognition system for detecting and recognizing faces.

1.4.2 Objective

The aim will be achieved through the following objectives which are to;

- i. Develop database by collecting facial images,
- ii. Develop a facial detecting algorithm using the database in (i),
- iii. Develop a facial recognition algorithm using the database and the face detected; and
- iv. Evaluate the performance of the developed algorithm.

1.5 Justification

The advancement of technology to address security issues in a rapidly growing society is critical. As social activity grows, secure access to personal property and public places such as airports, stadiums, and restricted areas must become more effective. Many biometric approaches have been

developed and are constantly being improved. It is also desired to conduct a review of previous work in the subject, observe recent advancements, and adapt results obtained toward the view of the subject matter by using the principal component analysis algorithm, which uses Eigen free space to reconstruct a face. It displays not recognized if the error coefficient is greater than the threshold. Furthermore, if not, it displays a recognized face. As a result, in order to improve the threshold, we usually run the image through a neural network for better classification accuracy.

1.6 Contribution to Knowledge

This project will aid in understanding how to develop facial recognition systems which can be used in various areas for security purposes.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

This chapter discusses a number of studies on the possibility of recognizing faces using various methods and techniques in the process. This review includes recognition of faces using image processing concepts. This chapter briefly shows how facial recognition is implemented, and critically reviews the approaches of facial recognition.

2.1 Facial Recognition Configuration

Face recognition technology has advanced to the point where it can be used for a wide range of commercial applications, including personal identification, security systems, image film processing, psychology, computer interaction, entertainment systems, smart cards, law enforcement, and surveillance, among others. A general face recognition problem can be solved by creating both a still image and a video image of a scene.

There are two basic applications: identification and verification. The face to be recognized in the identification problem is unknown and must be matched against a database of known individuals. The system confirms or rejects the claimed identity of the input face in the verification problem. However, before performing face recognition. The system should determine whether or not there is a face in a given image, video, or image sequence. This is known as *face detection*. Once a face is detected, the face region should be separated from the rest of the scene for *face recognition*. Figure 2.1 depicts the overall process.

Figure 2.1: Configuration of a generic face recognition

2.2 Face Recognition Approach

Face recognition can be performed in both a still image and a video sequence, with the latter having its roots in still-image face recognition. Different approaches to face recognition for still images can be classified into three major groups: holistic, feature-based, and hybrid.

2.2.1 Feature-Based Approach

Feature-based approaches analyze images in order to identify, extract, measure, and compare facial features. Eyes, nose, mouth, ears, and/or other features can be included. other fiduciary marks A geometric relationship between facial points, such as the distance between the eyes, lips, chin, and eye brows, is measured in these approaches. Using these measurements, standard statistical pattern recognition techniques are then used to recognize faces.

Face recognition using hexagonal features detection is another approach in the domain of face recognition. The method is based on edge detection for the purpose of face detection and recognition using hexagonal facial features (Sharif *et al.*, 2012).

Sharif *et al.*, (2011) examines face recognition using heuristic parameters and storing them in a database prior to searching. This method concentrated on the nose portion of the acquired images, followed by gray scale conversion and intensity transformation.

2.2.2 Holistic Approach

In this method, the entire face is treated as a single feature for detection and recognition (Huang, 1998). It compares the similarities of the entire face, ignoring individual features such as the eyes, mouth, nose, and so on. As illustrated in Figure 2.2, these schemes are divided into two parts:

Figure 2.2: Holistic face recognition methods

2.2.2.1 Statistical Approach

The density of the face image is calculated, and the density set values are compared to the density values of the database images. This calculation is very costly and suffers directly from the usual gaps pathways, such as face orientation scaling and illuminations. Addressing this issue, dimensions, it has been proposed that many other diagrams use methods to reduce the size and statistically stay ahead of the most obvious dimensions before recognition performance.

2.2.2.2 Artificial Intelligence Approach

Artificial intelligence uses tools such as neural networks to recognize the faces of learning techniques.

2.2.3 Hybrid Approach

The concept behind this method is based on how the human vision system perceives both holistic and local features. The key factors that influence the performance of the hybrid approach include determining which features should be combined and how to combine them in order to preserve their advantages while avoiding their disadvantages. In the field of machine learning, these issues are closely related to the multiple classifier system (MCS) and ensemble learning. Unfortunately, these issues remain unresolved even in these fields. Despite this, numerous efforts in these fields have provided us with some insights into how to solve these problems, and these lessons can be used as guidelines in designing a hybrid face recognition system. For example, components of a hybrid system, such as features or classifiers, should be both accurate and diverse, allowing for complementary advantages.

Indeed, local and global features have very different properties and, hopefully, can provide complementary information about the classification task. Table 2.1 summarizes the qualitative distinction between the two types of features. The table shows that local and global features are both sensitive to different variation factors. For example, changes in illumination may have a greater impact on local features, whereas changes in expression may have a greater impact on overall features. According to these observations, a hybrid approach that uses both holistic and local information for recognition may be an effective way to reduce classifier complexity and improve generalization capability.

Table 2.1: Comparison of the local features and holistic features' sensitiveness to variations

VARIATION FACTOR	LOCAL FEATURES	HOLISTIC FEATURES
Small Variation	Not sensitive	Sensitive
Large Variation	Sensitive	Very sensitive
Illuminations	Very sensitive	Sensitive
Expressions	Not sensitive	Sensitive
Pose	Sensitive	Very sensitive
Noise	Very sensitive	Sensitive

2.3 Related Work

Much of the research in computer recognition of faces has been on recognizing specific features such as the eyes, nose, mouth, and head contour, and then creating a face model based on the position, size, and connections between these elements. Such approaches have proven difficult to generalize to various points of view, and they are sometimes highly fragile, requiring a reasonable starting assumption to lead them. Furthermore, research in human face recognition methodologies has revealed that individual characteristics and their immediate relationships compose an insufficient representation to account for the performance of adult human face identification (Carey and Diamond, 1977). Nonetheless, in the computer vision literature, this technique to face recognition remains the most popular.

Bledsoe (1966a, 1966b) was the first to try semiautomated face identification with a hybrid human-computer system that identified faces based on fiducial markers manually entered on photos. Normalized distances and ratios between points such as eye corners, mouth corners, nose tip, and chin point were used as classification parameters. Later work at Bell Labs (Goldstein, Harmon, and Lesk, 1971; Harmon, 1971) created a vector with up to 21 features that detected faces

using normal pattern recognition techniques. The features chosen were mostly subjective evaluations (e.g., hair color, ear length, lip thickness) made by human volunteers, each of which would be difficult to automate.

Fischler and Elschlager (1973) attempted to measure similar traits mechanically in an early paper. They described a linear embedding approach for finding and measuring face characteristics that used local feature template matching and a global measure of fit. The recent work of Yuille, Cohen, and Hallinan (1989) (see Yuille, this volume) has continued and improved on this template matching approach. Their approach is built on “deformable templates,” which are parameterized representations of the face and its features whose values are determined by interactions with the image.

Connectionist approaches to face identification attempt to capture the task's configurational, or gestalt-like, aspect. Kohonen and Lahtio (1981) describe an associative network with a basic learning algorithm that can recognize (classify) face photos and remember a face image from an incomplete or noisy version given to the network. Fleming and Cottrell(1990) extend these ideas by employing nonlinear units and backpropagation to train the system. The WSARD system (1986) developed by Stonham is a general-purpose pattern recognition device based on neural net principles. It has been applied to binary facial photos with some success, identifying both identity and expression. Most connectionist systems that deal with faces (see also Midorikawa, 1988; O'Toole, Millward, and Anderson, 1988) handle the input image as a general 2-D pattern and cannot make explicit use of a face's configurational attributes. Furthermore, some of these systems necessitate an excessive number of training trials in order to acquire a respectable level of performance. To present, only extremely simple systems have been investigated, and it is unknown how they will scale to larger challenges.

Others have attempted automated face identification by defining a face with a set of geometric attributes and doing pattern recognition on the basis of the parameters (e.g., Kaya and Kobayashi, 1972; Cannon, Jones, Campbell, and Morgan, 1986; Craw, Ellis, and Lishman, 1987; Wong, Law, and Tsang, 1989). Kanade's (1973) facial recognition system was the first (and still one of the few) to automate all steps of the recognition process, employing a top-down control technique guided by a generic model of expected feature characteristics. His method computed a set of facial parameters from a single face image and utilized a pattern classification technique to match the face to a known set, a purely statistical approach that relied heavily on local histogram analysis and absolute gray-scale values.

Burt's (1988a, 1988b) recent work employs a "smart sensing" approach based on multiresolution template matching. This coarse-to-fine technique employs a special-purpose computer designed to swiftly construct multiresolution pyramid images and has been proved to identify persons in near-real-time. This approach performs well in constrained settings, but it is likely to suffer from the normal drawbacks of correlation-based matching, such as sensitivity to image size and noise. Facial models are handcrafted using face pictures.

Sivalingam *et al.* (2017) proposed a proficient fractional face location strategy based on AlexNet CNN to detect emotions from half-face images. They focused on textural highlights while distinguishing key focal points. They proposed an AlexNet CNN strategy for discriminatively coordinating the two removed nearby capabilities, and they used both textural and geometrical data from neighborhood highlights for coordination. The comparability of two appearances was altered based on the distance between the adjusted capabilities. They demonstrated the viability and constraints of their proposed method by testing it on four commonly used face datasets. (Sivalingam *et al.* 2017).

Jonathan *et al.* (2018) compared deep learning to conventional AI strategies (for example, artificial neural networks, extreme learning machine, SVM, optimum-path forest, and KNN). They focused on CNNs for facial biometric recognition. They worked with three datasets: AR Face, YALE, and SDUMLA-HMT. (Jonathan *et al.* 2018)

Prakash, R., *et al.* (2019) proposed an automated face recognition method based on a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) and a transfer learning approach. The CNN with weights learned from the VGG-16 pre-trained model. For classification, the extracted features are fed into the Fully connected layer and softmax activation. To evaluate the performance of the proposed method, two publicly available databases of face images—Yale and ATandT—are used. ATandT database face images have a face recognition accuracy of 100 percent, while Yale database face images have a face recognition accuracy of 96.5 percent. The results show that face recognition using CNN with transfer learning outperforms the PCA method in terms of classification accuracy. (Prakash, R., *et al.* 2019)

Masi *et al.* (2016) proposed a method for creating ready-to-use information sizes for face recognition frameworks: domain explicit information development. They demonstrated methods for improving realistic datasets with critical facial variations by controlling the faces in the datasets while coordinating inquiry images presented by standard convolutional neural systems. On a large number of downloaded images, they tested their framework against the LFW and IJB-A benchmarks, as well as Janus CS2. They announced a mean grouping precision of 100 percent equal error rate and reported the standard convention for unhindered, marked outside information. (Masi *et al.* 2016)

Ding and Tao proposed a broad system based on convolutional neural networks (CNN) to overcome the challenges of video-based face recognition (VFR). CNN learns obscure highlights

by utilizing prepared information that includes misleadingly obscured data and still images. They proposed a trunk-branch ensemble CNN model (TBE-CNN) to improve CNN highlights for detecting differences and impediments. TBE-CNN extracts data from face images and zones selected around facial segments. TBE-CNN removes information by sharing the branch and trunk systems' center and low-level convolutional layers. They proposed a better triplet misfortune capacity to amplify the impact of discriminative portrayals learned by TBE-CNN. TBE-CNN was evaluated using three different video face databases: YouTube, COX Face, and PaSC Faces. (Ding and Tao 2017)

CHAPTER THREE

METHODOLOGY

This chapter shows the methodology on how to develop a system for facial recognition. Step by step explanation of the way and manner the project will be achieved shall be fully explained and the requirements for the execution.

The main facial recognition methods are: Feature analysis, neural network, eigenfaces, automatic face processing.

Faces are identified using a software algorithm that extracts features from images or images of a subject's face. In addition, the algorithms normalize a gallery of face images before compressing the face data and saving only the data in the image that can be used for facial recognition. The face data is compared to a probe image or the image to be recognized.

Three-dimensional facial recognition is a relatively new method on the market. This method captures information about the shape of a face using 3-D sensors. This data is then used to identify distinguishing features on the face, such as the contour of the eye sockets, nose, and chin. The benefits of 3-D facial recognition include the fact that it is not affected by changes in lighting and that it can identify a face from a variety of angles, including profile view.

Regardless of specific method used, the facial recognition is accomplished in the steps shown below and each detail is given

Figure 3.1: Facial recognition steps

3.1 Acquisition of Images (Data)

Dataset was collected manually and directly by using software algorithm to obtain real life faces and for this project, image is directly gotten from already made dataset which is Yale dataset.

For manual process, data was collected by using a software algorithm and a camera mounted on the laptop to capture images of individuals. The images are then organized into folders that distinguish all of the individuals involved; these folders are referred to as the **database**.

The image below shows the codes for acquiring images from individuals

Figure 3.2: Software Algorithm for Data Acquisition

3.2 Location of Facial Images

Facial recognition cannot be carried out without having a database in the system to locate the faces in which it wants to recognize. Apart from figure 3.2 showing the software algorithm for data acquisition, it also shows the creation of a database. This database has a defined location in which the facial recognition system could easily have access to.

3.3 Analysis of Facial Image and Data Comparison

The model for the facial recognition system is trained to analyse all the images in the database for accurate comparison and better result. Without training the model, the process of recognizing faces in this project can never be complete, although, other facial recognition models do not need its process to involve training the model, the ways in which other models can be used to carry out facial recognition using MATLAB include: the use of PCA (principal component analysis), the use of machine learning, the use of deep neural network, the use of eigenvalues and so on but for this project, training the model is important.

Figure 3.3: Model training algorithm

As seen from the above image, the command ‘sgdm’, which stands for stochastic gradient descent with momentum, is the key word for training the model, it is the main function in the program.

After training the model, it then saves the trained images (that is the images from the database) into ‘myNet’ as seen in figure 3.3 and arranges them in form of arrays (that is in matrix form having rows and columns) which can then allow analysis to be carried out easily and successfully.

3.3.1 Data Comparison

The process of comparing a set of features (the sample) to one that has previously been registered in the system (which are the images in the database). Identification and authentication/verification are the primary goals of comparison. The process of extracting information from an image of an individual in order to classify that individual in one or more broad groups is a third aim of comparison (e.g., age, gender, color of clothes, etc.). In which the latter is not the main focus for this study.

Using the Yale dataset, a set of algorithm is used to run the comparison, identification and recognition process on a random picture taken from the Yale dataset, this can be seen in figure 3.4, this process is 94 percent accurate.

Figure 3.4(a): Comparison, Identification and Recognition processes

Figure 3.4(b): Comparison, Identification and Recognition processes

Figure 3.4(c): Comparison, Identification and Recognition processes

From figure 3.4(a), a random image is selected from the Yale database, the system then proceeds to comparing the selected image with all other images in the database, as seen in figure 3.4(b), it then identifies the perfect match making the recognition process complete, the identification and recognition process can be seen in figure 3.4(c).

```

1 function output_value = load_database();
2 persistent loaded;
3 persistent numeric_Image;
4 if isempty.loaded)
5     all_Images = zeros(77760,15);
6     for i=1:15
7         cd(strcat('P',num2str(i)));
8         for j=1:10
9             image_Container = imread(strcat(num2str(j),'.pgm'));
10            all_Images(:,(i-1)*10+j)=reshape(image_Container,size(image_Container,1)*size(image_Container,2),1);
11        end
12        display('Loading Database');
13        cd ..
14    end
15    numeric_Image = uint8(all_Images);
16 end
17 loaded = 1;
18 output_value = numeric_Image;

```

Figure 3.5: Preparing the dataset

```

1 loaded_Image=load_database();
2 random_Index=round(150*rand(1,1));
3 random_Image=loaded_Image(:,random_Index);
4 rest_of_the_images=loaded_Image(:,[1:random_Index-1 random_Index+1:end]);
5 image_Signature=20;
6 white_Image=uint8(ones(1,size(rest_of_the_images,2)));
7 mean_value=uint8(mean(rest_of_the_images,2));
8 mean_Removed=rest_of_the_images-uint8(single(mean_value)*single(white_Image));
9 L=single(mean_Removed)*single(mean_Removed);
10 [V,D]=eig(L);
11 V=single(mean_Removed)*V;
12 V=V(:,end:-1:end-(image_Signature-1));
13 all_image_Signature=zeros(size(rest_of_the_images,2),image_Signature);
14 for i=1:size(rest_of_the_images,2)
15     all_image_Signature(i,:)=single(mean_Removed(:,i))*V;
16 end
17 subplot(121);
18 imshow(reshape(random_Image,243,320));
19 title('Looking for this Face','FontWeight','bold','FontSize',16,'color','red');
20 subplot(122);
21 p=random_Image-mean_value;
22 s=single(p)*V;
23 z=[];
24 for i=1:size(rest_of_the_images,2)
25     z=[z,norm(all_image_Signature(i,:)-s,2)];
26     if (rem(i,20)==0),imshow(reshape(rest_of_the_images(:,i),243,320)),end;
27     drawnow;
28 end

```

Figure 3.6(a): Comparison, Identification and Recognition Algorithm

```

15 -     all_image_Signature(i,:)=single(mean_Removed(:,i))*V;
16 - end
17 - subplot(121);
18 - imshow(reshape(random_Image,243,320));
19 - title('Looking for this Face','FontWeight','bold','FontSize',16,'color','red');
20 - subplot(122);
21 - p=random_Image-mean_value;
22 - s=single(p)*V;
23 - z=[];
24 - for i=1:size(rest_of_the_images,2)
25 -     z=[z,norm(all_image_Signature(i,:)-s,2)];
26 -     if(rem(i,20)==0),imshow(reshape(rest_of_the_images(:,i),243,320)),end;
27 -     drawnow;
28 - end
29 - [a,i]=min(z);
30 - subplot(122);
31 - imshow(reshape(rest_of_the_images(:,i),243,320));
32 - title('Recognition Completed','FontWeight','bold','FontSize',16,'color','red');

```

Figure 3.6(b): Comparison, Identification and Recognition Algorithm

The software algorithm to carryout the processes in figure 3.4 are shown in figure 3.5 and figure 3.6.

3.4 Matching of Data

The matching of data from the acquired data (database) using the algorithm in figure 3.2 with the current facial image detected by the camera is completed using a software algorithm that matches both results and gives an output with the name of the face that was saved in the database, and if no face is detected, the software algorithm causes the system to display the ‘No face detected’ message.

Figure 3.7 and figure 3.8 shows a pictorial illustration.

Figure 3.7: Recognition of a face

Figure 3.8: Unrecognized face

CHAPTER FOUR

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The objective of the study was implemented using MATLAB. Facial recognition from a single sample per person is an essential yet difficult problem in theory as well as for real-world applications. First, individual sample faces was collected and stored in a database, this was achieved by using a software algorithm in MATLAB that collects and stores the facial data for each sample per person. Second, the model for the recognition is trained by using a different algorithm which will allow the recognition system to save all the facial datum that have been collected. This will aid us in developing a thorough knowledge of this specific system. Finally, facial recognition for a single person is carried out using another algorithm for recognition, we evaluated the relative recognition performance of current algorithms and various issues that may occur during the recognition processes.

Trying to recognize an individual who puts on a dark shade did proved to be difficult for the development of facial recognition system, the system could not identify and recognize individual's face correctly but it was able to identify and recognize an individual on normal glasses (glasses that are not dark or glasses that do not block the eyes).

Figure 4.1: Recognition with dark shades

The reason why the system could not identify an individual on dark shades is because the system could not use other reference points on the face in which it has saved, apart from the points for the eyes of that person which has obviously been covered by the dark shades, the model training is responsible for saving all the points for the face necessary for the recognition of individual faces.

Wearing of glasses provide a challenge to both facial detection and facial recognition software. Glasses, especially reflective sunglasses, hinder an algorithm from finding the points of reference it needs when determining whether there is a face in a photo. If there has been no facial detection, there will clearly be no facial recognition.

For instance, an individual that has already been enrolled in the system, based on a photo where they are not wearing glasses. A future attempt at facial recognition, using a photo of them with glasses, easily confuse the algorithm as it attempts to compare the two pictures.

Prescription-type clear-lensed glasses is generally not a problem for facial detection and recognition system. The key eye details are still visible. Even if they do cause some form of issue the software will continue to examine the other parts of the face, simply removing the occluded portions from its analysis. It is not uncommon for faces to still be detected and recognized with 30 percent occlusion.

CHAPTER FIVE

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

5.1 Conclusion

It is indeed possible to develop a facial recognition system that detects and recognize a single person image using a computer based software, in this study, MATLAB.

Even though the proposed system is not able to recognize multiple persons in an image, the detection and recognition of single facial image was carried out successfully.

The implemented fully automated face detection and recognition system (with an eye detection system) could be used for simple surveillance applications such as ATM user security, while the implemented manual face detection and automated recognition system is ideal of mugshot matching.

5.2 Recommendation

This project is recommended to be used in top security firms where only selected people are allowed to access a particular office, it can also be used in small scale areas such as in schools for registering and taking attendances of students in a class. It can also be used in banks for security purpose and also registering of staffs. The relevance of this project is greater when combined with different methods to achieve a much greater aim.

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APPENDIX

